

ENTREPRENEUR WOMAN – FUTURE DEVELOPER

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Abstract: regardless of the field in which women are employed today, the development of entrepreneurial and business skills in each of them and the promotion of new entrepreneurial networks is a requirement of the time. This article examines the role of an enterprising woman in the development of society from a philosophical point of view.

Keywords: entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial culture, income, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial activity.

The study, which first studied the role of Uzbek women in the life of the state and society from a political point of view, focused on the importance that women's economic activities positively affect their activation even in the political life of society[1]. It provides conclusions on strategic tasks related to women in Uzbekistan, legal guarantees for increasing the political activity of women in the process of democratization of the country, features of political leadership in women, the opportunities created by the state, the increased social activity of women, their urgent importance in gaining a worthy place in the family and society, the solution to the problems.

Although the research focuses on one branch of the economy, namely the activities of women in small business and entrepreneurship and in the field of work, to this day there are no fully revealed scientific analyzes of their participation in the socio-economic life of society, and also the problem in question has not been studied in a complex way scientifically in the historical aspect.

Today, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, the Association of Business Women of Uzbekistan and its subordinate branches, the Liberal of Uzbekistan, in

cooperation with the "women's wing" of the Democratic Party, conducts international activities aimed at developing comprehensive cooperation with a number of international organizations accredited by the Ministries of Foreign Affairs and Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, women's centers of foreign, primarily economically developed countries, as well as International women's movements that work to protect the family and women's rights.

"In 2017, a joint plan was established between the women's committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Unicef Organization on promising joint actions on issues of improving the effectiveness of pilot projects in regions with the highest negative indicators in order to strengthen mutually beneficial relations on social protection issues, work with families in a targeted manner"[2].

As we have already described above, the economic thought of female entrepreneurs present in the country, there is a dialectical unity of their spiritual and material ground. It seems to us that they cannot be separated from each other or put opposite. Thanks to dialectical unity in the development of society, the economic thinking of young people is being formed and developing.

Research on the spiritual and material ground of modern women's entrepreneurship at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan, first of all, has a legal status as a real material and spiritual wealth of women; secondly, the fate of these riches is being developed by giving it into the hands of female businessmen and entrepreneurs on the basis of organizing various forms of ownership; thirdly; fourth, the formation of modern women from the requirements of their long-standing traditions, values and global economy; fifth, we can see that the demand for the creation of new national concepts and models of ensuring the economic security of young people in times of economic crises is increasing; and the next is the need to arm young people with economic thinking during the transition This determines the need for a large-scale study of women's entrepreneurship.

It is advisable to express the place of female entrepreneurs in the formation of their economic thinking through the following example from the point of view of the international division of Labor.

In the specific aspects of the development of the economic thinking of women entrepreneurs, the export quota is the gross output of export volume, the growth of which is competitive in the national economy, on which multi-ownership is based, and shows that in world markets the buyer is increasing the share of products. This, in turn, increases the material interest of the female entrepreneur, leading them to the faster formation of a new economic thought in their economic consciousness.

The peculiarities of the development of gender equality of female entrepreneurs are that the main goal pursued by it when buying imported goods from the outside and introducing them into the interior of the country is to meet the domestic needs of the country or to reproduce and export (sell back to other countries). In our opinion, developed countries are engaged in the export of raw materials and advanced technologies from other countries, processing in themselves and selling them to another state. This process in international trade is also among the objective factors in the formation of the economic thinking of the youth of our country. In the formation of economic thinking, the negative aspects of this factor are more than positive, since not meeting the domestic needs of the country in exchange for the development of domestic technology, living only in exchange for imports poses a great threat to the economic security of the country and opens a wide path for its future transformation into a dependent country.

As an objective factor in the development of women's gender equality in the formation of economic thinking of women entrepreneurs and businessmen of the country;

1) by recognizing the development laws of international trade, it is necessary to integrate with it on the principles of the national economy;

2) maintaining a balance in the dialectic of exports and imports, the importance of focusing on the exploitation of export opportunities at a level that does not harm the economic life of our country;

3) the need to follow the path of evolutionism in conquering not large world markets at once, but regional markets with the production and sale of competing and

purchasing goods. It interacts with more than 140 countries in our country, 80 of which have the potential to export goods and services.

Specific aspects of the development of women's Economic Thought also manifest themselves in global economic problems. According to him, as a result of the integration of the national economy of each country with the world economy, the system of positive or negative consequences arising in the socio-economic life of the nation and the people changes. So it will be possible to conditionally divide it into the following groups. Firstly, processes in the " Society-Nature " system, and secondly, society can be divided into socio-economic problems within it.

In our opinion, to solve this problem, it is required to create and introduce technologies that save economic resource. This, in turn, influences the economic consciousness of young people, motivating the movement of economic thought.

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